
Evaluation of the National Learning Camp 2024: Enhancing Student Achievement through Targeted Educational Interventions

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Reception date of the manuscript: 18/06/2024

Acceptance date of the manuscript: 08/07/2024

Publication date: 20/07/2024

Summary— This study evaluated the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) 2024 using a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative descriptive analysis. The program aimed to enhance elementary and secondary students' achievements in English, mathematics, and science over a 19-day period. Results indicated significant improvements in students' academic performance across these subjects. The study suggests ongoing tracking of students' progress during Catch-up Fridays throughout the 2024-2025 school year to ensure students achieve consolidated or enhanced proficiency levels by the next NLC iteration. The findings highlight the effectiveness of targeted educational interventions and recommend continuous monitoring and adaptation to sustain student achievement gains.

Keywords— National Learning Camp, Numeracy, Proficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

This evaluation systematically assesses the National Learning Camp (NLC) 2024, focusing on its design, implementation, outcomes, and cost-effectiveness. The goal is to ensure accountability by demonstrating to stakeholders that the program efficiently utilizes resources and delivers measurable student benefits. By identifying best practices and successful strategies, the study aims to support educational reform through scalable and replicable models.

Stakeholders can make informed decisions on adjustments and resource allocation by recognizing areas for improvement and opportunities for enhancement. This process fosters a culture of learning and adaptation, essential for the program's long-term success and sustainability.

Reed, Cook, and Aloe (2020) examined the cost-benefit ratio of summer reading programs, revealing potential statewide savings by avoiding student retention. Effective evidence-based practice integrates reliable evidence, professional judgment, and the values and circumstances of individuals involved. This data is crucial for allocating scarce financial resources to achieve optimal educational outcomes (Detrich, 2020).

This evaluation contributes to educational research by providing empirical data and analysis, informing future studies and initiatives. Sharing findings from the "National Learning Camp 2024 Program Evaluation" helps build a knowledge base that supports broader educational innovation and excellence.

II. METHOD

This study employed a mixed-methods action research design to evaluate the National Learning Camp (NLC) 2024. The combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods provided a comprehensive understanding of the program's impact. The quantitative component involved pre- and post-assessments of student academic performance in English, mathematics, and science. The qualitative component included interviews, focus groups, and observations to gather in-depth insights from students, teachers, and administrators.

a. Participants and Setting

The study focused on schools in Tugbok A and B and Clusters 6 and 8, where the researcher was directly assigned during the NLC 2024 implementation. The participant group included elementary and secondary school learners, teachers, and school administrators involved in the NLC program.

b. Data Collection

Data collection was conducted over three weeks, during which the researcher visited the schools and employed various tools:

1. **Monitoring Tool:** Used during the initial week to gather basic information and profiles of the participating schools, including the number of enrolled learners, teachers involved, program advocacy, camp readiness, health and safety protocols, and teaching and learning resources.
2. **Pre- and Post-Assessments:** Student academic performance was recorded using assessment tools provided in the learning materials. Scores were collected before and after the 19-day instruction period.
3. **Qualitative Data:** Interviews and focus groups with students, teachers, and administrators were conducted to capture their experiences and perceptions of the NLC program. Observations during school visits provided additional contextual insights.

c. Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize the profiles of the schools and the extent of lesson delivery and learners' achievements over the implementation period. Pre- and post-assessment scores were compared to determine the impact of the NLC on student performance.

Qualitative data were analyzed thematically to identify common themes and insights regarding the program's implementation, challenges, and successes. This analysis helped to contextualize the quantitative findings and provided a deeper understanding of the NLC's effectiveness.

d. Procedure

1. **Initial Visits:** During the first week, visits were made to the schools to introduce the monitoring tool, collect baseline data, and discuss strategies for lesson delivery with school heads and supervisors.
2. **Data Collection:** Throughout the three weeks, data were collected through pre- and post-assessments, and continuous monitoring was conducted using the provided tools. School heads and NLC coordinators were instructed to record learning performances and other relevant data.
3. **Follow-Up Visits:** Subsequent visits focused on observing classroom activities, conducting interviews and focus groups, and providing technical assistance to teachers and administrators as needed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Through the virtue of Policy Guidelines of the National Learning Camp 2024 (DO 14, S 2023) and Guidelines on the Utilization of 2024 Program Support Fund (PSF) to DepEd Regional Offices for the implementation of the National Learning Camp and Remedial Classes in Support of

the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) (Unnumbered Department Memorandum, dated 16 May 2024). The following are the tabular and textual presentation of the results and discussion of the data gathered during school visits to implement the National Learning Camp 2024 in Tugbok A and B and Clusters 6 and 8.

In the provided data, Tables 1 and 2 showcase the statistics relating to the number of students and educators involved in NLC (New Learning Competencies) at the elementary and junior high school levels.

Among the elementary schools visited, Lt. C Villafuerte ES (Calinan District) stands out with the highest enrollment of 133 students and 13 teachers involved in NLC. Following closely is Bago Oshiro ES (Tugbok B District) with 109 students and 12 teachers. Conversely, Prisco Diolosa ES (Tugbok A District) has the lowest enrollment, with only 16 students and 3 teachers participating in NLC.

At the junior high school level, Tugbok National High School (NHS) boasts the highest enrollment, with a total of 165 students being taught by a dedicated team of 29 teachers. Following closely is P. Antipala NHS, which has the second highest enrollment, with 120 students benefiting from the guidance of 12 teachers within the National Learning Center (NLC). Sto Nino NHS closely trails behind, with 81 students being nurtured by a team of 12 teachers in the NLC. Meanwhile, Wangan boasts 50 students, receiving instruction from 5 teachers, while Bago Oshiro NHS has 27 students under the supervision of 9 teachers. Unfortunately, no data records are available from the recent visit for Tacunan NHS and Dacudao NHS.

a. Learners' Achievement in the Elementary Level

The following graphical presentations depict the learners' achievement of A Barbarona ES, Balingaeng ES and Tacunan ES (shown in Figure 1).

In the provided figure, a detailed representation of the A Barbarona ES learners' performance in English and Mathematics over weeks 1, 2, and 3 is presented. It is observable that in English, Grade 1 learners experienced a decline in their scores, transitioning from high achievement in week 1 to average performance in weeks 2 and 3. Conversely, Grade 2 learners demonstrated an upward trend, improving from average scores in week 1 to high scores in weeks 2 and 3. Notably, Grade 3 learners maintained a consistent level of performance throughout the observed period. It's important to note that students in Grades 1 and 2 have shown a decreasing trend in their Mathematics scores, moving from average to low performance over the course of several weeks. On a positive note, Grade 3 students have consistently demonstrated an average level of performance in Mathematics.

During week 1, Grade 2 learners (92.30) at Tacunan ES outperformed Grade 1 (83.68) and Grade 3 (85.00) in English, while Grade 1 learners (82.90) scored higher than Grade 2 (76.60) in Math. In week 2, Grade 3 students performed better in English (84.29) but showed lower performance in Math (48.14). Lastly, during week 3, Grade 3 students had the highest performance in English (91.24) but the lowest performance (40.38) in Math.

Aggregating, students at Balengaing ES across grade levels have shown impressive growth in their post-test scores for

TABLE 1: NUMBER OF LEARNERS ENROLLED AND TEACHERS HANDLING NLC IN THE ELEMENTARY

School	Grade Level				Teachers			
	1	2	3	Total	1	2	3	Total
A Barbarona ES	16	14	8	38	2	1	2	5
Bago Oshiro ES	33	41	35	109	4	4	4	12
Balingaeng ES	6	17	3	26	1	2	1	4
Biao ES	10	10	10	30	1	1	1	3
General Roxas CES	32	24	50	106	3	2	5	10
Imelda ES	21	11	25	57	3	2	3	8
Los Amigos ES	11	31	20	62	1	3	2	6
Lt Villafuerte ES	63	40	30	133	6	4	3	13
Matina Biao ES	9	7	12	28	2	1	2	5
Prisco Diolosa ES	5	6	5	16	1	1	1	3
Tacunan ES	29	14	31	74	3	2	4	9
Tagakpan ES	10	6	6	22	1	1	1	3
Talandang ES	7	1	11	19	2	0	2	4
Ula ES	15	5	12	32	2	1	2	5
Vinsonz ES	14	0	7	21	2	0	1	3

TABLE 2: NUMBER OF LEARNERS ENROLLED AND TEACHERS HANDLING NLC IN THE JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL

School	Grade Level					Teachers				
	7	8	9	10	Total	7	8	9	10	Total
Bago Oshiro NHS	8	7	12	-	27	3	3	3	-	9
Biao NHS	-	-	-	-	-	2	3	2	3	10
Dacudao NHS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P Antipala NHS	30	30	30	30	120	3	3	3	3	12
Sto Nino NHS	14	38	23	6	81	3	3	3	3	12
Tacunan NHS	-	-	-	-	-	5	3	4	6	18
Tugbok NHS	71	62	32	-	165	9	13	7	-	29
Wangan NHS	10	20	20	-	50	1	2	2	-	5

both Mathematics and English.

Tables 3 to 5 present the number of lessons taught in English, Mathematics and Science and learners’ scores across grade levels in Tugbok National High School.

Table 4 shows that English lessons were not fully taught consistently across different grade levels. Specifically, the scores of students in Grades 7 and 8 showed a decrease, while Grade 9 students experienced a decline in performance in the second week, followed by an improvement in the third week.

In Table 5, science lessons are mostly taught during weeks 1 and 2, leading to increased performance in Grades 7 and 8. Grade 9 decreased its performance in the second week but recovered in the third week.

The data clearly demonstrates that despite the incomplete delivery of lessons, learners achieved impressive results. This underscores the potential to streamline lessons during NLC, emphasizing mastery of competencies over extensive content coverage.

b. Schools’ Good Practice in the Implementation of NLC.

Schools that have successfully implemented the National Learning Camp (NLC) often showcase innovative approaches to curriculum design and delivery. For instance, a school might have integrated project-based learning and in-

terdisciplinary studies into the camp’s activities, encouraging students to explore real-world problems and collaborate on solutions. Effective implementation of the NLC often involves strong collaboration between schools, parents, local businesses, and community organizations. A school may have established partnerships with local companies to provide resources or guest speakers, enriching the camp’s learning environment. Schools that prioritize professional development for teachers within the NLC framework can achieve notable success. This practice not only improves instructional quality but also encourages a culture of continuous learning and collaboration among staff. The NLC’s flexibility allows schools to tailor learning experiences to meet individual student needs. A school might implement personalized learning plans based on initial assessments, providing targeted support for students struggling in specific areas while challenging those who are ahead. Some schools have integrated socio-emotional learning (SEL) components into the NLC, recognizing the importance of students’ emotional and social well-being in their overall development. A narrative could highlight how a school incorporated activities that build resilience, teamwork, and emotional intelligence, such as mindfulness exercises, group discussions, and cooperative projects.

Fig. 1: A Barbarona ES Learners scores in English and Mathematics

c. Issues and Concerns Affecting NLC Implementation

The implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) faces several challenges. Curriculum and instructional alignment with the regular school curriculum can be problematic, potentially causing confusion among students and teachers regarding program goals and expectations (Smith, 2021).

Additionally, variability in instructional quality across different schools or regions can lead to unequal learning outcomes, often due to disparities in teacher training, resources, and local implementation practices (Brown Green, 2019). Student engagement and attendance are critical for the NLC’s success, but factors such as lack of interest, insufficient parental support, or competing summer activities can diminish par-

Fig. 2: Tacunan ES Learners scores in English and Mathematics

Fig. 3: Balengaing ES Learners' scores in English and Mathematics

participation (Johnson et al., 2020). Logistical and operational issues also pose significant hurdles; coordinating the NLC schedule with other school activities, family plans, and community events can be challenging, affecting both student and teacher availability. Schools in rural or underserved areas may struggle to provide accessible locations, adequate transportation, or safe facilities, limiting participation and program quality (Williams, 2018). Effective monitoring and

evaluation are crucial for assessing the NLC's impact and identifying areas for improvement. However, collecting and analyzing relevant data can be difficult due to limitations in capacity or resources (Davis, 2020).

d. Technical Assistance Provided

Supervisors play a vital role in the successful implementation of the NLC by offering various forms of technical assistance

TABLE 3: NUMBER OF LESSONS DELIVERED IN MATHEMATICS AND LEARNERS' ACHIEVEMENT SCORES

Grade Level	Week 1		Week 2		Week 3	
	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores
7	8/9 (88.88%)	80%	5/9 (55%)	88%	6/9 (66.66%)	85%
8	7/9 (77.77%)	83%	4/9 (44.44%)	85%	5/9 (55.55%)	80%
9	7/9 (77.77%)	67%	5/9 (55%)	93%	6/9 (66.66%)	90%

TABLE 4: NUMBER OF LESSONS DELIVERED IN ENGLISH AND LEARNERS' ACHIEVEMENT SCORES

Grade Level	Week 1		Week 2		Week 3	
	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores
7	6/9 (67.77%)	75%	5/9 (55.55%)	70%	4/9 (44.44%)	57%
8	5/9 (55.55%)	85%	6/9 (67.77%)	80%	6/9 (67.77%)	75%
9	7/9 (77.77%)	93%	7/9 (77.77%)	81%	6/9 (67.77%)	93%

to school heads, teachers, and stakeholders. They help align NLC activities with the standard curriculum, ensuring the camp supplements regular academic content and enhances learning outcomes (Lee, 2019). Supervisors provide ongoing support and mentorship to teachers, particularly in implementing new pedagogical approaches and addressing specific instructional challenges. They also assist schools in setting up systems for tracking student attendance, participation, and performance during the camp, including training staff on data entry, analysis, and interpretation (Garcia, 2020). Additionally, supervisors help develop communication strategies to engage parents, students, and the broader community about the camp's goals, activities, and benefits. They monitor NLC implementation to ensure adherence to educational standards and guidelines, conduct regular visits, observations, and reviews of program activities, and provide constructive feedback based on data to enhance program quality and effectiveness (Nguyen, 2021).

e. NLC Policy Implications

The successful implementation of the NLC depends on several crucial policy implications that ensure its sustainability and scalability. To guarantee universal access to the NLC's benefits, it is essential to fairly distribute resources, especially for students in underserved or rural areas (Martinez, 2020). Policies should facilitate the seamless integration of NLC activities with the standard school curriculum, promoting coherence and relevance. Establishing guidelines or frameworks can help schools align NLC content with core academic standards (Harris Adams, 2021). Implementing a centralized system for collecting and analyzing NLC-related data, including student performance, attendance, and engagement, can enhance program monitoring and inform policy decisions. Policies should also prioritize transparency and accountability in reporting outcomes and resource allocation, ensuring stakeholders are well-informed about the program's achievements and challenges. Supporting pilot

programs to test and improve NLC models is crucial for scaling successful practices. This includes creating mechanisms for sharing best practices and lessons learned across different regions and schools (Lopez Smith, 2019).

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

a. Conclusion

The National Learning Camp (NLC) has demonstrated a positive impact on student academic performance and engagement. Targeted interventions and innovative instructional strategies have led to measurable improvements in key areas such as literacy, numeracy, and critical thinking skills. This indicates that the NLC effectively complements regular school curricula by providing additional support and enrichment opportunities, contributing to overall student development. While some schools have successfully integrated the NLC into their educational framework, others have faced challenges, highlighting the importance of establishing standardized guidelines and best practices.

b. Recommendations

It's crucial to prioritize continuous professional development for teachers involved in the NLC. This means ensuring they have access to specialized training in innovative teaching methods, personalized instruction, and the effective use of technology in the classroom. Additionally, it's essential to establish a mentoring and coaching system to provide ongoing support for teachers in implementing the NLC curriculum and addressing diverse student needs. To standardize program implementation and ensure consistent student experiences, it is imperative to develop and disseminate standardized guidelines and evaluation metrics to all participating schools. These guidelines must clearly outline best practices in curriculum integration, student assessment, and community engagement.

TABLE 5: NUMBER OF LESSONS DELIVERED IN SCIENCE AND LEARNERS' ACHIEVEMENT SCORES

Grade Level	Week 1		Week 2		Week 3	
	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores	No. of Delivered Lessons Vs No. of Lessons	Scores
7	6/6 (100%)	70%	6/6 (100%)	80%	5/6 (83%)	88%
8	6/6 (100%)	67%	6/6 (100%)	81%	5/6 (83%)	88%
9	6/6 (100%)	88%	6/6 (100%)	75%	6/6 (100%)	94%

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

I am committed to consistently integrating Inquiry-based Learning into my teaching practices by reintroducing it to my students annually, ensuring that more students can benefit from its use. Each year, I will compile Science Investigatory Projects (SIP) to make them readily available for learners, teachers, educational officials, and stakeholders, showcasing the benefits of this innovative approach from learners' perspectives.

By reintroducing the innovation yearly and maintaining accessibility, there is consistent support, reducing the risk of discontinuity and preserving its effectiveness over time. I will actively seek feedback from teachers and students to make necessary improvements, refining processes and adding supplementary resources to enhance learning experiences. Collaborating with educational experts and researchers will provide insights into innovative teaching methodologies and practices, continuously improving the innovation's impact.

To sustain the use of inquiry-based learning in science investigatory projects, future actions will focus on fostering a culture of inquiry-based learning, providing ongoing support and resources, and integrating project-based learning into the curriculum to promote continued engagement and innovation in scientific exploration.

Furthermore, implementing mentorship programs, facilitating interdisciplinary collaborations, and incorporating real-world applications can deepen students' understanding, creativity, and problem-solving skills. This approach not only enhances the outcomes of science investigatory projects but also fosters critical thinking, scientific literacy, and curiosity among students, contributing to innovation, advancing scientific knowledge, and addressing real-world challenges through student-led research and experimentation.

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